

The Earliest Grammars of Sri Lanka Portuguese

As primeiras gramáticas do português do Sri Lanka

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Abstract: The timing and mechanism of the development of South Asian features in Sri Lanka Portuguese is examined through the lens of two early 19th C grammarians: Berrenger, apparently a native speaker, and Callaway, an Anglophone missionary. Both authors portray a typologically European rather than South Asian language. Evidence shows that both authors deliberately set out to do this, Berrenger by selecting conservative, European variants, Callaway by borrowing from standard Portuguese and by calquing from English. The fact that neither author is consistent, however, allows the conclusion that many of the South Asian features of present-day Sri Lanka Portuguese were already in play by the early 19th C, competing with more conservative, typologically European features, over which they eventually predominated to produce modern Creole.

Keywords: Sri Lanka Portuguese; Creolization; Contact-induced change.

Resumo: O tempo e o mecanismo do desenvolvimento de traços do sul da Ásia no Português do Sri Lanka são examinados a partir da análise de duas gramáticas novecentistas: Berrenger, aparentemente um falante nativo, e Callaway, um missionário anglófono. Ambos os

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autores representam uma língua mais europeia do que propriamente do sul da Ásia. Evidências sugerem que ambos os autores deliberadamente assim o fizeram, Berrenger selecionando variantes conservadoras europeizantes, Callaway, por sua vez, pegando palavras emprestadas do português e fazendo decalques do inglês. Contudo, o fato de nenhum dos autores serem, nos permite concluir que muitos traços do sul da Ásia do português do Sri Lanka já estavam ativos no começo do século XIX, competindo com traços tipologicamente europeus, mais conservadores, sobre os quais acabaram por se sobrepor, resultando no crioulo moderno.

Palavras-chave: Português do Sri Lanka; criouliização; mudança induzida pelo contato.

1 Introduction

Modern Sri Lanka Portuguese exhibits Dravidian typology due to the influence of the indigenous languages, Sinhala² and Tamil (Smith 1979). The timing and mechanism for the development of Dravidian features has not been established. Did they develop as part of the original creolization or at some subsequent time via adstrate influence? If the latter, was this a rapid convergence as posited by Bakker (2000a, 2000b) or a more gradual process? While the Creole literature of the 19th century does not in general exhibit Dravidian typology, it is doubtful, that this literature, particularly the large quantity produced by anglophone missionaries, faithfully represented the spoken creole of the time (Smith 1979: 213-218, 1998: 19-24). Because it is based largely on this literature, Dalgado's grammar (1900) does not present a clear picture of developments in the spoken Creole during the previous century. Some of the differences between 19th century literary creole and the colloquial creole of the 20th century are listed in Table 1. This paper examines the earliest known grammars of Sri Lanka Portuguese, produced at the beginning of the 19th century, in order to shed light on these issues.

The earliest works on Ceylon-Portuguese, as the Creole was known, are Berrenger's (1811) grammatical description accompanied by conversational and textual examples, Callaway's (1818) vocabulary/phrasebook in English, Sinhala and Creole, Fox's (1819) vocabulary and grammatical sketch, and Callaway's (1820b) vocabulary/phrasebook (a revision of Callaway 1818, omitting the Sinhala data,

²Sinhala is a member of the Indo-Aryan subfamily of Indo-European, but it exhibits Dravidian features developed through contact.

reducing the exemplification and making many changes to the Creole data)³. As Fox's grammatical sketch is very brief, it will not be examined here in detail, but mentioned only when it provides relevant information.

³Reinecke et al. (1975) list also Fox's *Primeiro ensinos ne lingua portugueza de Ilha de Ceylon* (2nd ed. 1818), which I have been unable to locate and which is not listed by Worldcat.

	19 th C Literary	20 th C Colloquial (Smith 1979)
Marking of NP function	prepositions <i>de</i> GEN/INS <i>ne</i> LOC <i>com</i> ASSOC <i>per</i> ACC/DAT	case suffixes and postpositions - <i>su</i> GEN (<Ptg. <i>sua</i> '3SG.GEN.F') -(<i>juu</i>) <i>ntu</i> LOC/ASSOC (<Ptg. <i>junto</i> 'together; next to') - <i>pa</i> ACC/DAT (<Ptg. <i>para</i> 'for; to'; marker of various types of complement) <i>vɔɔnda</i> INS (<Ptg. <i>banda</i> 'side') clause-final <i>falaa(tu)</i> (QUOT) (< Ptg. <i>fala-</i> 'say; speak')
Complementizer(s)	clause-initial <i>que</i>	- <i>voo</i> (INDEF) (<Tamil = <i>oo</i> , idem) <i>ki-(ta-)</i> (NMLZ) (<Ptg. <i>que</i> REL/COMP)
Relative clauses	right branching with relative pronoun <i>que</i> , <i>quando</i> etc.	left branching; no relative pronoun, occasional <i>ki-</i> (<Ptg. <i>que</i>)
Conditional	clause-initial <i>se</i>	phrase final <i>see/sara</i> (< Ptg. <i>se</i> 'if'/? <i>sera</i> 'BE.FUT.3SG') / verbal prefix <i>kam(da)-</i> (< Ptg. <i>quando</i> 'when')
Copula	usually present	variable – usually absent
Main constituent order (unmarked)	usually SVO	SOV
Articles	variable use of definite <i>o</i> , indefinite <i>hum(a)</i>	Numeral <i>uŋ</i> '1' (<Ptg. <i>um</i> DEF.M.SG) used as indefinite specific; no definite.
Coordination	conjunction <i>e</i> (both clausal and NP conjunction)	conjunction <i>kum/kun</i> (NP conjunction) (<Ptg. <i>com</i> 'with'); Ømarked or PFV (- <i>tu</i> <Ptg. <i>junto</i> 'together' ⁴) conjunctive participle (clausal conjunction)
Polar questions	inversion (variable) subordinating conjunctions e.g.	final indefinite particle <i>voo</i> ; more commonly, intonation alone
Adverbial clauses	<i>videque</i> 'because' <i>quando</i> 'when' <i>dispois de</i> 'after' / <i>maisdianti</i> 'before'	various formations conditional: <i>kii-pa see</i> / <i>kii-pa kam-fala</i> 'because' (Lit. 'what-DAT COND' / 'what-DAT COND-QUOT') <i>V+ɔɔras</i> (<Ptg. <i>horas</i> 'hours') 'when V-ing', <i>INF+dispoos/prumeer</i> (<Ptg. <i>depois</i> 'after' / <i>primeiro</i> 'first'); 'after' / before V-ing'

2 Berrenger

The author of the first known Creole grammatical treatment is something of a mystery. No personal information is supplied, and we cannot even ascertain whether Berrenger (B) was a man or a woman, as only the surname is given. For the sake of expediency, I shall assume B was female. Several pieces of evidence indicate, that she was a Burgher. The title-page dedication “To the English Gentlemen in the Civil and Military Service on Ceylon. By their much Obliged and most Obedient Servant.” signals that she was not a member of the British colonial establishment. Moreover, the final paragraph of the [unpaginated] Preface reveals that she was not a mother-tongue speaker of English:

With regard to the style of this Book, I hope that the English Gentlemen and the public will excuse it, if they find some inaccuracies of expression or Idioms improper or foreign to the English Language – I only endeavoured to be understood, and I believe, I have succeeded.

Berrenger is a known Burgher surname, though more commonly spelled Berenger, with a single <r>. The baptismal records for the Dutch Reformed Church at Wolvendaal, Colombo list one “Pierre (Petrus) (Peter) Berrenger” (with <rr>) as the father of four children baptised between 1798 and 1810 (Mottau 1962: 42). Although nothing identifies this man or his wife as our author, we can conclude that there were at least two Burgher candidates of an appropriate age at the time of publication.

Berrenger’s preface mentions that this is a second edition “which I now offer to the public” (1811: unpaginated), implying that the first edition was unpublished.

The work consists of two main parts: a grammatical description and a series of phrases, “dialogues”, and texts. Interspersed are lexical lists of various sorts (e.g. focussing on a semantic field or grammatical category). The grammatical description compares the Creole (“Corrupted Portuguese”) to standard (“High”) Portuguese. A sample is presented in Figure 1. B[errenger]’s knowledge of standard Portuguese seems derived entirely from Vieyra (various editions and publication dates, e.g. 1777), whose organization she follows and from whom she plagiarizes copiously. The dialogues and lexical lists are similarly taken from Vieyra. Most of the texts are translations of English passages in Gladwin (1801) and Theibault (1806). The source of one text remains unidentified.

⁴A second possible source of PFV *-tu* is an allomorph of the Ptg. past participle marker (normally *-du*) occurring in some irregular verbs, such as in *feito* ‘done’ (INF *fazer* ‘to do’) or *dito* ‘said’ (INF *dizer* ‘to say’). A third possible source is the configuration of PST + PTCP seen in a large class of Tamil regular verbs, e.g. *kuḍu-tt-u* ‘give-PST-PTCP’. A fourth possibility is the Tamil perfective past participle marker, normally *-(i)ttu* in the Batticaloa dialect, as in *kuḍu-tt-ittu* ‘give-PST-[PTCP]-PFV.PST.PTCP’.

2.1 Orthography

B's Creole orthography is based on the standard usage found in Vieyra, with variable changes that likely reflect creole pronunciation at the time, such as the merger of sibilants /s/ and /ʃ/, and occasional traces of Dutch influence, like the encoding of /i/ as <ie>, as in *trezie-vez* 'thirteenth' (1811: 8), cf. *trezi* 'thirteen' (1811: 7). B's typographer does not seem to have had access to the tilde, which is simply omitted in standard Portuguese examples, as in *amarao* 'love:PST:3PL' (1811: 24), or replaced by an acute accent, as in *amaô* 'love:PRS:3PL' (1811: 24). Erroneous accents are also occasionally found in B's standard Portuguese examples, e.g. *esté* 'this' (1811: 12), *â* *qúal* 'to which' (1811: 14), *si eu tívera* 'if I had had' (1811: 19). Inconsistent accent use is also found in B's Creole, e.g. *rivé de mézéz* (1811: 73) vs. *ribe de meze* (1811: 72) 'upon the table', *anda foré* 'go away' (1811: 75) vs. *fore de caze* 'out of the house' (1811: 72). The acute accent and the rarer grave accent, as in *curé* 'to run' (1811: 77), appear most frequently on final vowels, particularly <e>, and likely indicate unstressed [ə], as, for example, in *tinhé ~ tinhe* (auxiliary) (1811: 35, < Ptg. *tinha*; mod. SLP *tɪŋa*), *rainhé* 'queen' (1811: 5, < Ptg. *reinha*; mod. *rɪiŋa*), *trinté* 'thirty' (1811: 7, < Ptg. *trinta*; mod. *triinta*), *dié* 'day' (1811: 97, < Ptg. *dia*; mod. *diiya*), *idadé* 'age' (1811: 99, < Ptg. *idade*; mod. *idaay*), *chuvé ~ chuva* 'rain' (1811: 101, < Ptg *chuva*; mod. *cuuva*).

2.2 Morphosyntax

B's morphosyntax reflects a language of unmistakably European typology, similar in many respects to the later works of the Anglophone missionaries: it is characterized by prepositions, complement clauses introduced by *que*, left-branching relative clauses with a marker *qui/que*, conditionals with clause-initial *se*, a mostly present copula, SVO word order, conjunctions *e* 'and' and *o* 'or' used for both nominal and clausal conjunction, and adverbial clauses introduced by conjunctions.

B generally works from Vieyra's English glosses and does not appear to know Portuguese grammar. For example, in his discussion of impersonal verbs Vieyra mentions the use of the reflexive pronoun *se* with an active verb, giving the example *Louva-se o capitão* (praise-IMPR the captain) 'They praise the captain.' (1777: 106). This construction is not found in the Creole, and B's translation (1) of Vieyra's English gloss is not, in fact, impersonal. B's occasional borrowings from Vieyra's Portuguese examples similarly reveal a lack of grammatical knowledge. Confronted with unfamiliar lexical material, B is unable to parse Vieyra's Portuguese expressions. Thus in (2) B copies Vieyra's standard progressive construction representing an unfamiliar meteorological phenomenon (replacing the the verb *está* with the Creole present tense marker). If B had knowledge of Portuguese grammar, she should have been able to extract the verb *neva-* and create the grammatical Creole equivalent *te neva*. In (2b), B simply borrows the entire phrase, while at the same time miscopying *está* as *sta*.

- (1) **Elotros te gava por captam.**
 3PL PRS praise ACC captain
 ‘They praise the captain.’ [B 1811: 89] ⁵
- (2) a. **Te neva-ndo.**
 PRS SNOW-ndo
 ‘It snows.’ [B 1811: 143; Vieyra’s original: *Está neva-ndo* be.3SG.PRS
 snow-PPL.PRS (1777: 326)]
- b. **Na senhor mas agora sta gea-ndo.**
 no sir but now *sta* freeze-PPL
 ‘No sir, but it freezes now.’ [B 1811: 143. Vieyra’s original: *não senhor,*
mas agora está gea-ndo. ‘no sir, but now be.3SG.PRS freeze-PPL.PRS’
 (1777: 327)]

Outside the grammatical description, B’s translation of phrases and texts does not usually slavishly follow the English (nor, a fortiori, the Portuguese). For example, in the section ‘To wish ill’ Vieyra has *O diabo te leve* ‘The devil take thee’ (1777: 244), in place of which B gives (3). Occasionally, however, a tendency to calque from the English gloss appears, as in (4). Unlike English *ask*, modern Creole *pidii* takes a direct nominal complement (not a PP complement). Portuguese *pedir* and Dutch *vragen*, *verszoeken*, *aanvragen*, *inroepen* (all ‘ask for’) similarly take direct nominal complements. While it is true that ANIMATE direct complements are marked in the Creole by the marker *par/per/por* (a continuation of Portuguese usage), the insertion of *por* before an inanimate complement in the second clause of (4) looks to be triggered by B’s English original. Finally, occasionally B’s Creole cannot be accurate. In (5), for example, we see instances of adjectival gender and number agreement with the antecedent (*linguiça-s* ‘sausage-PL’, which in Portuguese is FEMININE). The Creole, like other creoles, lacks grammatical gender entirely; and only nouns may be marked for PLURAL, never adjectives. The example also contains the Portuguese copula form *sta* (be.3SG.PRS), which does not survive in the Creole. (See discussion in 3.4.1 below.) These standardisms do not all come from Vieyra, who has (6), and are perhaps evidence of a secondary source or of editorial assistance from someone more familiar with Portuguese.

⁵Punctuation and the use of upper and lower case in examples taken from Berrenger and Callaway have been silently normalized. Morph-by-morph glosses are supplied, but the English equivalents are original, except where noted. As explained, these are not free translations, but the source from which both Berrenger and Callaway generated their Creole data. Where possible, the parts of the examples that illustrate the point in question are bolded.

- (3) **Eu tem contenti se diabo lo quebra bosse piscos.**
1SG be happy if devil FUT break 2.GEN neck
'I should be very glad if the devil break your neck.' [B 1811: 93]
- (4) **Eu noque pedi por um none, eu ja pedi por um boca de Pan.**
1SG NEG ask for/ACC a lady 1SG PST ask for a
mouthful of bread
'I *asked for* a bit of bread, not a lady.' [B 1811: 163]
- (5) **Eu ja cume algu-a sta muyto sáboros-a-s**
1SG PST eat some-F *sta* very tasty-F-PL
'I have eat some [sausages] they are very good.' [B 1811: 139]
- (6) **Já comi algum-a-s, ella-s saõ muito bo-a-s**
Already eat.PST.1SG some-F-PL 3.F-PL be.PRS.3SG very good-F-PL
'I have eaten some, they are very good.' [Portuguese, Vieyra 1777: 324]

The Sri Lanka Indo-Portuguese speaking community is complicated by the fact that the Creole was adopted as the home language of the Dutch,⁶ who wrested control of coastal Sri Lanka from the Portuguese in a series of operations between 1638 and 1658. The Dutch had no allegiance to either Portugal or the Catholic Church; in fact they were antagonistic to both. Dutch single men posted to the island sought wives from the existing creole community, however, and their progeny grew up using Creole. As noted, circumstantial evidence points to Berrenger's membership in this community. Consequently, she likely had no contact with standard Portuguese speakers, nor would there have been any reason to promulgate a standard-influenced Creole variety, if indeed that were possible given B's apparently meager knowledge of the standard. Logically, then, B's description and examples represent features current in the Creole of the late 18th or early 19th century. Nevertheless, the form of language presented is clearly curated. A striking piece of evidence for this is the fact that Berrenger does not mention postnominal *su* as a marker of genitive in the grammatical description section of the work, and uses it only very occasionally in texts, as for example (7). The formation is ubiquitous in Asian Portuguese-based creoles (Baxter & Bastos 2012, and the further references therein) and must already have been present in the early Portuguese-based Malabar pidgin postulated by Clements (2000), likely in competition with the standard prepositional marker *de*. Postnominal *su* is the only genitive formation in modern SLP, except for lexicalized forms of *de*, as in *bɔvardaav* 'watermelon' < Ptg. *abobora d'agua* ('melon *de* water').

⁶Hugo Cardoso (p.c., July 2016) points out that the same may have happened in other Indo-Portuguese communities that fell under Dutch control; cf. Dalgado 1917.

(7) **Que.lay tem voss mestri su nomi?**How be.PRS 2.GEN master **GEN** name

'What is your master's [i.e. teacher's] name?' [B 1811: 142]

The fact that Berrenger's description is filtered through the lenses of Portuguese grammatical terminology and English glosses limits our ability to see South Asian characteristics that the Creole may have possessed, but evidence that certain such features were present, at least variably, as will be seen in section 4.

3 Callaway

Rev. John Callaway was appointed to the Ceylon branch of the Wesleyan Missionary Society in 1814 (The Missionary Register 3(1815): 475) arriving on the island in mid-1815 (Findlay & Holdsworth 1921, V: 60). He soon produced two vocabulary/phrasebooks for "Ceylon-Portuguese" (Callaway 1818, 1820b). As noted above, the latter is essentially a streamlined edition of the former, a work that is itself derivative, being "first composed in the English and Cingalese languages only" (1818: iv, probably referring to an earlier edition of Callaway 1820a). Despite the temporal proximity, Callaway appears to have drawn little, if anything, from Berrenger (1811). An examination of Callaway's two works reveals a great deal about his *modus operandi*, particularly (but not exclusively) in the many places where they differ in the Creole translation offered for the same English word/expression.

The following passage from the introduction to Callaway 1818 reveals his general approach and philosophy:

The native youth, it is believed, will peruse these pages with peculiar advantage, as the various subjects are carefully arranged; and the English sentences are composed in the style of polite conversation. For the latter excellence, the writer owns himself generally indebted to some European publications, in popular esteem. (1818: iii.)

The "European publications" from which Callaway drew inspiration are likely to have been language guides such as Castro's *Grammatica anglo-lusitanica & lusitano-anglica* (1751) or Boyer's *The complete French master for ladies and gentlemen* (1782). Such works commonly contained lists of words and phrases which various authors freely copied from one another. (Indeed, many of the phrases in these works are found also in Berrenger's model, Vieyra). For example, Callaway shares with Castro and Boyer a section entitled "To thank and compliment, or shew (a) kindness," containing sentences such as 'I render you a thousand thanks;' 'I desire you to be free with me;' 'Have you any commands for me?' and 'Let us forbear compliments,

I pray.’ None of the 33 phrases in this section is original with Callaway. His other sections appear to be similarly derivative. Callaway’s methodology, then, was to begin with a stock set of English words and phrases and to ascertain their equivalents in the Creole. Indeed, such is the implication behind his remark that “In every instance, it has not been possible to *translate the English* in the most literal manner; but always a similarity, and, in general, an exactness of meaning has been carefully conveyed.” (1818: iii, emphasis mine). He acknowledges the assistance of a local Assistant Missionary William A. Lalmon,⁷ whom Findlay & Holdsworth identify as “a Burgher physician of Swiss descent on his father’s side” and an early convert (1921, V5: 61). Callaway also acknowledges “the kindness of other individuals” (1818: iv), but provides no further insight into how the Creole (and Sinhala) equivalents were obtained.

It is clear, as we shall see, that Callaway did not rely solely on the input of local consultants. His knowledge of Portuguese orthography, likely unfamiliar to local speakers, would have placed him in the role of expert. His membership in the colonial elite and his position as a learned member of the Wesleyan Mission would also have induced a degree of deference on the part of local people. Modern linguistic field workers know to be wary of issues of power and hierarchy, and they employ elicitation techniques that centre on authentic local material. Callaway was a man of his times, however, lacking the insights subsequently developed by field linguistics and sociolinguistics.

3.1 *Lexicon*

Significant differences are found between the lexical lists of Callaway (1818) and Callaway (1820b). For example, in the section dealing with parts of the body, roughly 75% of the entries differ between the two *Vocabularies*, a figure which seems typical of the other sections as well. One-third of these differences involve substantially different words for the same item (i.e. not just orthographical differences, the addition/deletion of an alternate term, or the presence/absence of an article). Table 2 lists some of these. Berrenger’s and modern Creole equivalents are given where they are known. Callaway’s later Vocabulary removes a number of standard (non-Creole) elements found in his earlier work:

- The occasional presence of the definite article (e.g. *o Corpo, os Ventas de Naris*),

⁷ *Lalmon*, according to Callaway, but *Lallman* is recorded in other sources (e.g. Wesleyan Methodist Church 1818: 420; Missionary Register 9(1821): 77).

- Occasional mutated plural forms (e.g. *Feiçoens*),
- Calques from English, such as *Olha Dente-s* (eye tooth-PL) ‘eye teeth’ (cf. Ptg. *dente canino*, Du. *hoek tand*, lit. ‘angle tooth’),
- Reliance on standard Portuguese etyma, such as *Trachea*, *Polegar*, *Punho*, *Costela*, *Joelho*, and *Artelho de Pe*, replaced in 1820b by more Creole terms.

These items are consistent with a methodology that begins with a list of glosses and seeks to find Creole equivalents, resorting to expedience to fill gaps.

It is also clear that the 1820 Vocabulary is generally more reflective of actual Creole, though it continues to be influenced by standard Portuguese and contains a number of obvious inaccuracies: what, for example, is the rationale behind the unpacking of items such as *Mandretu* ‘right hand’,⁸ listed in 1818, into its historical source, *mão direito* in 1820b?⁹

3.2 Orthography and phonology

The orthography of both *Vocabularies* is only somewhat reflective of creole phonological reality, which lacked the standard Portuguese distinctions between /e/ and /ei/ (<e> and <ei>), between /s/ (<ss>, <ç>) and /ʃ/ (<x>), between /ʎ/ (<lh>) and /j/ (<y>), and between nasalized and oral vowels, all of which appear in Callaway’s spellings. Neither Vocabulary consistently represents standard distinctions, however.

In addition to these issues, Callaway’s orthography is often inconsistent, as seen in Table 2 the representation of final /a/ varies between <e> in *barbe* ‘beard’ and <a> in *testa* ‘head’ (and many more such examples); similarly, final /i/ is sometimes represented as <e> as in *dente* ‘tooth’, and sometimes as <i>, as in *pele* ‘skin’ (Ptg. *pele*); in the section “Fruits and Fruit Trees” (1820b: 15); the same suffix is spelled three different ways in *Coquera* ‘a Cocoa-nut Tree’, *Panigeiro* ‘a Palm Tree’ (modern *panageera*), and *Mangero* ‘a Mango Tree’.

3.3 Callaway’s morphosyntax: Calquing from English

Moving to Callaway’s phrases and dialogues, one encounters a new set of problems. Most notably, the apparent English-based calquing seen throughout the mission-related literature finds its earliest examples here.

⁸In Modern Sri Lanka Portuguese *mandreetu* means ‘right’; this may already have been true in Callaway’s time.

⁹This is one of the relatively few cases in which Callaway (1818) resembles modern Creole more than Callaway (1820). A few examples of genuine Creole features do occur in Callaway (1818), however, doubtless as a result of assistance from native speakers. Such features are sometimes decreolized, as here, in Callaway (1820). Syntactic examples are seen in (90) and (101).

Tab. 2: Examples of differences in the lexical lists of Dalgado 1818 and 1820b.

Callaway (1818)	Callaway (1820b)	Gloss	Berenger (1811: 120-121)	Modern Creole (if known)	Etymology (Ptg. unless otherwise noted)
The Parts of the Human Body/O Partes de Corpo Humano (pp. 10-13)	Parts of the human Body/PARTES DE HUMANO CORPO (pp 3-4)		Partes de Corpo Humane		
o corpo	corpo	'the body'	[corpo]	koorpu	corpo
testa, ou fronte de cabeça	testa	'the forehead, or fore-part of the head'	testa	tɛɛsta	testa 'head'; fronte 'forehead'
feiçoens de rosto	fessaões de rosto	'the features'			feições
os ventas de naris	boracos de nariz	'the nostrils'	ventas		ventas
olha dentes	[no entry]	'the eye-teeth'			[calque:] olho 'eye'; dentes 'teeth'
[no entry]	lingoa	'the tongue'	lingua, lingo	liingu	lingua
trachea, ou canal de respiração ou de folgo	nerva que te tira folga	'the windpipe'			nervo 'nerve'
barba	tucinho	'the chin'	facino, mentan		barba 'beard'; ?tucinho 'bacon; lard'

Tab. 2: Examples of differences in the lexical lists of Dalgado 1818 and 1820b.

barbe	barbe	'the beard'	barbe(s)	baarva	
piscos	pescoso	'the neck'	piscoss	gargaantu/gɔrgal ¹⁰	pescoso; early mod. Du. Gorgel
ceio	peito	'the bosom'	mama	peetu	seio 'breast, bosom'; peito 'breast, chest'
peito, mama	peith, mama	'the breast'	peito	peetu	mama; peito
omber	ombra	'the shoulder'	ombros 'shoulders'	ɔombra	ombro
braço	braso	'the arm'	braço, braso	maam (braasu = 'fathom')	braço
cotovelo	cotovelha	'the elbow'	cotevelo chonde		cotovelo
mandreto	maõ direito	'the right hand'		mandreetu maam ¹¹	mão direito
maõ isquerda	maõ iscarda ¹²	'the left hand'		mayskaarda maam	mão esquerda
onha	unha	'the nail'	unha, unhe	uujna	unha
lado	ilharga	'the side'	ilhargas 'sides'	(iyaarga 'beside')	= ilharga; lado

Tab. 2: Examples of differences in the lexical lists of Dalgado 1818 and 1820b.

perna	‘the thigh’ / ‘the thigh, the leg’	perna	pεerna	perna	
juelho	injuvejo ¹³	‘the knee’	ingevejo	injuvey / unjuvey	joelho
perna	[see above]	‘the leg’		pee ¹⁴	perna; pé
artelho de pe	schenkle	‘the ankle or ankle-bone’			Du. schenkel ‘shank’
pelle	pele	‘the skin’		pεeli	pele

3.4 Existential

The deictics *ali/ala* ‘there’ are found regularly in Callaway’s existential expressions, as in (8 - 9).

- (8) a. **Ala nontem nehum divida de aquel.** [C 1820b: 33]
 b. **Ali nontem ne.hum duvida de aquel.** [C 1818: 87]
 There NEG.be no doubt of that
 ‘**There** is no doubt of it.’
- (9) a. **Alla nontem nade que pode acha semtem trabalho.** [C 1818: 145]
 b. **Ala non.tem nada que pode acha sentem**
 There NEG.be nothing that HBL get NEG.PPL.be
travalha. [C 1820b: 44]
 work
 ‘**There** is nothing to be had without pains.’

This usage is not standard Portuguese, modern Creole, Sinhala or Tamil. Is it possible that it is from Dutch?¹⁵ At first glance, Dutch *er*, a locative pronoun more or less equivalent to English *there*, appears to be a candidate source for the existential use of *ali/ala*. In Dutch, however, a variety of verbs may be used with existential *er*, for example *staat* ‘stands’ in (10) and *hangen* ‘hang’ in (11). In English the use of verbs other than *BE* in existential expressions is not found except in archaic/poetic usage, as in *On yonder hill there stands a maiden*, the first line of the folk song *O*,

¹⁴The difference between *gargaantu* and *gɔrgal* is unclear.

¹⁴The modern terms for ‘left’ and ‘right’ obviously derive from ‘left hand’ and ‘right hand’.

¹⁴A typographical error in Callaway (1820b) places the Sri Lanka Portuguese for these entries next to the gloss for the following entries.

¹⁴< ? *um joelho* ‘a knee’; < ? *em joelhos* ‘kneeling’. Thanks to Hugo Cardoso (p.c., July 2016) for pointing out this second etymology, from Dalgado (1913: 5), who records similar forms in other Luso-Asian creoles. In modern Sri Lanka Portuguese ‘kneel’ is rendered as *injuvey-ntu santaa* (knee-LOC sit). It is possible that *injuvey* originally meant both ‘kneel’ and ‘knee’, but songs, which often reflect earlier features of the language, also use a phrase for ‘kneel’: *santaa na injuvey*.

¹⁴As in many languages (and most South Asian languages) there is no distinction between the basic terms for ‘hand’ and ‘arm’ or ‘foot’ and ‘leg’.

¹⁵I thank an anonymous reviewer of another paper for raising this possibility.

No *John*.¹⁶ It is notable that Callaway's examples align with English in allowing only *teem* 'be; have' in existential expressions. The case for Dutch influence here is accordingly weak.

- (10) *Er staat een paard in de gang.*
There stand.PRS.2/3SG INDEF horse in DEF corridor.
'*There is* [lit. *stands*] a horse in the corridor.' [Dutch. Popular song by André van Duin]
- (11) *Er hangen schilderij-en aan de muur.*
There hang.PRS.PL painting-PL on DEF wall
'*There are* [lit. *hang*] paintings on the wall'. [Dutch. Lingren 2009: 16]

It is weakened further by the absence of such usage in Berrenger, where only subjectless forms of *tem* 'be' are found for the existential construction, with no expletive *ala orali*¹⁷ (12, 13). No expletive deictic is found in either standard Portuguese or modern Creole (14, 15)

- (12) *Tem linguice-s e pequenino pастey-s.*
be.PRS sausage-PL CNJ little patty-PL
'*There are* some sausages and petty-paties.' [B 1811: 138]
- (13) *Lo tem aqui disti?*
FUT be here of.this
'*Is there* of it?' (Ptg. *ha lá disso?*) [B 1811: 67; for discussion of B's use of FUT, see 4.1.2]
- (14) *∩rta-ntu kokeera teem?*
compound-LOC coconut.palm be.PRS
'*Are there* coconut palms in the compound?' [Modern SLP¹⁸; author's 1974-5 field notes, item 5047]

¹⁶Deictic use of *there* + verb is, of course, fine in modern colloquial English, as in the song lyric "*There stands the glass that will ease all my pain.*" (*There stands the glass.* Russ Hull, Mary Jean Shurtz and Audrey Greisham 1953).

¹⁷*Alá* appears in one example. *Alá tem otros.* 'There are some others,' in which it is actually deictic, as in the Portuguese model *Lá há outras* (Vieyra 1777: 329), which Berrenger erroneously repeats as *Lá hé outros* (1811: 147).

¹⁸Unless otherwise noted, field data is extracted from recorded free conversations.

- (15) **Aka-pa un kaavs teem.**
 that-DAT one principle be.PRS
 ‘*There is* a principle for that.’ [Modern SLP; author’s 1974-5 field notes, item 5201]

3.4.1 Inversion

While modern Creole signals polar interrogatives with intonation alone or with the indefinite particle *vo* (Smith 2013: 118), both Callaway and Berrenger variably employ inversion. Inversion in Dutch places the subject after the main verb if no auxiliary is present. This formation was possible earlier in English, but in modern English (which includes Callaway’s time), inversion is possible only with an auxiliary or with the main verbs *BE* and *HAVE*; otherwise a dummy auxiliary *DO* is used to support inversion. Generally, Callaway’s examples of inversion are of the English type: the subject is placed after the auxiliary, if there is one (16). In the absence of an auxiliary, the subject is placed after the main verb *tem* ‘have, be’ (17, 18), and for other verbs, after the tense particle, as though it were a stand-in for English *DO* (19-21).¹⁹ Inversion is variable in both *Vocabularies*; thus (19b) exhibits no inversion.

- (16) **Pode vosse faze penna-s?**
HBL 2 make pen-PL
 ‘*Can you* make pens?’ [C 1818: 148]
- (17) **Tem ali algum carta-s par mi?**
be there some letter-PL for 1.ACC/DAT
 ‘*Are there* any letters for me?’ [C 1818: 149]
- (18) **Tem aquel verdade?**
be that truth
 ‘*Is it* true?’ [C 1820b: 33]
- (19) a. **Te vosse entende per elle bemfeito?** [C 1818: 101]
PRS 2 understand ACC 3SG.M well
- b. **Vosse ja intinde per elle bemfeito?**²⁰[C 1820b: 38]
 2 *PST* understand ACC 3SG.M well
 ‘*Do you* understand him well?’

¹⁹Cf. Smith 2015, who discusses two exceptions in Callaway 1818.

(20) *Te elle nada bemfeito?*

PRS 3SG.M swim well

‘Does *he* swim well?’ [C 1818: 150]

(21) *Lo vos come inde mais?*

FUT 2SG eat still more

‘Will *you* eat any more?’ [C 1818: 91]

Berrenger also uses inversion to signal interrogatives, but B’s inversion is influenced by Dutch rather than by English (Smith 2015). In the absence of an auxiliary, B employs inversion with a variety of verbs, not just *tem* (22-24). In past sentences, B does place the subject after the tense marker *ja* (25), but inversion never occurs with *te* (PRS) or *lo* (FUT). Both *ja* (< Ptg. *ja* ‘already’) and *lo* (<Ptg. *logo* ‘soon’) originate from Portuguese adverbs, and could be expected to be more mobile than *te* (<Ptg. *está* be.PRS.3SG), which derives from a pre-verbal auxiliary. It is not clear, however, why *lo* patterns with *te* rather than with *ja*. In summary, while Berrenger’s use of inversion likely reflects Dutch influenced creole, Callaway’s inversion is calqued from English.

(22) *Te intende vosse portuguez?*

PRS understand 2 Portuguese

‘Do you understand Portuguese?’ [B 1811: 98]

(23) *Qui te falla gazette?*²¹

what *PRS say gazette*

‘And what *says the gazette?*’ [B 1811: 146]

(24) *Te cunecé vosse por eli?*

PRS know 2 ACC 3SG.MASC

‘Do you know him?’ [B 1811: 99]

(25) *Ja vosse intende bem.feito?*

PST 2 understand well

‘Did you understand well?’ [B 1811: 98]

²⁰The tense in this example is past, though Callaway’s gloss is the same as for (19a).

²¹In modern Creole, information in the discourse context can be right-dislocated. In (23), however, *gazette* is new information. Thus its finalposition is brought about by inversion rather than right-dislocation.

3.4.2 Tense particles as auxiliaries

The previous section discussed Callaway's treatment of tense particles *te* (PRS), *ja* (PST), *lo* (FUT) as though they were English auxiliaries in inversion. He further follows English usage in allowing a bare particle with an omitted main verb (26). In Berrenger, as in modern Creole, tense particles always appear with a following verb. Nor is there any counterpart of Callaway's usage in Dutch. Thus, for example, **Ik zal* 'I will' is not possible (Tonjes Veenstra, p.c. 2013).

- (26) **Eu lo. Muito bom.**
 1SG FUT very good
 'I *will*. Very good.' [C 1820b: 34]

3.4.3 Generic *hum(a)* 'one'

Callaway uses the numeral/indefinite *hum(a)* "one/a" as generic pronoun, on the model of English 'one'. Examples are seen in (27) and (28). Berrenger appears to use an unspecified subject to express generics (29), though examples are scarce. Certainly the use of *huma* does not reflect Portuguese usage,²² nor is a counterpart found in Dutch (van der Auwera, Gast, & Vanderbiesen 2012: 51). Callaway's usage is thus a calque from English.

- (27) (a.) **Mais per papia de aquel, hum miste sabe algum**
 (b.) **Mas per papia aquel, huma miste sabe alum**
 but INF speak of that one OBLG know some
cause de aquel. [C 1818: 146]
cousa-s de aquel. [C 1820b: 44]
 thing-PL of that
 'But to speak it [English], **one** must know something of it.'
- (28) **Hum podi confia per vosse.** [C 1818: 88]
Huma pode confia per vosse. [C 1820b: 33]
one HBL believe ACC 2
 '**One** may believe you.'
- (29) **Non podi intende eli que te falla.**
 NEG HBL understand 3SG NMLZ PRS say
 '**One** cannot understand what he says.' [B 1811: 98]

²²In Spanish, the numeral/article *uno* is used as a generic pronoun, but Portuguese employs the reflexive pronoun *se*.

3.4.4 *V-ndo* (present participle) = English *V-ing*

The present participle marker *-ndo* does not survive in modern Creole. Fox notes in his contemporary dictionary “Very few Verbs in this Language have a present participle active, the idea being conveyed by peculiar Idioms” (1819: 5). Nevertheless, Berrenger does use it to mark subordinate temporal clauses, as in (30). Callaway has two different uses (both rare), apparently modelled on the distribution of the English participle/gerund in *-ing*. In (31a) the preposition/infinitive marker *pera* (modern *pa-*) is followed by *V-ndo*, instead of by the base form of the verb, seen in the 1820 Vocabulary (31b), likely as an equivalent to the English phrase *by speaking*. A similar construction is seen in (32), where Callaway places the standard form *pelo* (‘to/for.DEF’, a contraction of *para+o*) before *V-ndo*. In standard Portuguese *para* takes an infinitival complement. Berrenger’s equivalent, *por*, is always followed by the bare verb. In (33) he translates ‘by *V-ing*’ with a relative clause. Callaway (1818)’s usage is therefore certainly erroneous.

Secondly, Callaway uses *V-ndo* following *tem* ‘be’ to mark the progressive, copying the English construction BE *V-ing* (34, 35).²³ Berrenger has no progressive marking (36, and B’s many full verbal paradigms), with the exception of the examples in (2) above, in which the unfamiliar verbs *neva-ndo* ‘snow-NDO’ and *gea-ndo* ‘freeze-NDO’ are copied directly from Vieira.

- (30) **Banker ja choma suve Mulher, falla-ndo cum rayva**
 banker PST call 3SG.GEN wife **say-NDO** with anger
vosse qui ja faze?
 you what PST do

‘The banker called his wife, *saying* angrily “what have you done?”’ [B 1811: 167, author’s translation]

- (31) (a.) **O mais levi modo per prende Ignres [sic] tem pera**
 (b.) **Mais leve modo per prende Ingres, tem per**
 DEF most easy way INF learn English be to/INF
papia-ndo tanto ves-es. [C 1818: 145]
papia tanto vez. [C 1820b: 44]
 speak-NDO many time-PL

‘The easiest way to learn English is *to speak* it often.’

²³The English stimuli/glosses in these examples are not progressive in form. In fact only a single BE *-ing* progressive form appears in the English glosses in Callaway 1818, 1820b even when the meaning is obviously progressive. The form was uncommon at the beginning of the Modern English period and subsequently increased in frequency, particularly after 1800 (Elsness 1994). While Callaway’s model, dating from well before 1800, hardly uses it, Callaway’s Creole *V-ndo* progressives indicate that it was current in his own usage.

- (32) **Hum te acha bom estame pelo *passia-ndo*.**
 one PRS get good stomach to.DEF *walk-NDO*
 ‘One gets a stomach by *walking*.’ [C1818: 115]
- (33) **Amezade qui ja entra *cuvice de astanto dinheiro...***
 friend *REL.PRO PST enter envy* of so.much money
 ‘The friend, *by coveting* this large sum...’ [B 1811: 159]
- (34) **Eu te alcança que o tempo tem *começa-ndo per ser***
 1SG PRS notice COMP DEF weather be *begin-NDO* INF be
nuvosu.
 cloudy
 ‘I see the weather *begins* to be cloudy’ [C 1818: 117]
- (35) **Par.que te vos brinca quando tem *anda-ndo ou***
 Why PRS 2 play when *be:PRS go-NDO* or
marcha-ndo?
walk-NDO
 ‘Why do you play *as you go* [lit. when *walking*]?’ [C 1818: 123]
- (36) ***Papia sempre bem o malo.***
speak always well or badly
 ‘*Be* always *speaking*, whether well or ill.’ [B 1811: 141]

3.4.5 Idioms

In addition to syntactic constructions, occasional examples occur of idiomatic expressions apparently calqued from English. I have already mentioned the compound *Olha Dentis* ‘eye teeth’ above. A phrasal example is (37). There is no Portuguese, Tamil or Sinhala precedent for this idiom in which striking a nail accurately is a metaphor for precision in language or action, but a Dutch equivalent exists: *de spijker op de kop slaan*. The fact that this item was dropped from the 1820 Vocabulary, however, suggests that it was not current among Creole speakers.

- (37) **Vosse ja prega o prego ne senal.**
 2 PST nail[V] DEF nail[N] LOC mark/signal(?)
 ‘You have hit the nail on the head.’ / ‘You have hit the mark.’ [C 1818: 88]

3.5 Morphosyntax: Inaccuracies

A second class of problems with Callaway's phrasal examples comprises blatant errors which point to an ignorance of Creole grammar on Callaway's part.

3.5.1 Copula

Standard Portuguese has two copulas: *ser* for inherent attribution and *estar* for temporary attribution. South Asian languages do not have this distinction, nor do they have a separate verb for 'have', possession being expressed with the copula/existential. In Indo-Portuguese creoles, forms of *ter* 'have' take over the role of *estar*. In Diu Portuguese the distinction between the two types of copula is maintained (Cardoso 2013a: 95-96) but in Korlai and Sri Lanka, forms of *ser* are not used for ordinary copulation. (In modern Sri Lanka Portuguese *seer* means 'become'). Modern Sri Lanka Portuguese has *teem* (PRS) *tijla* (PST) as copula/existential (< Ptg. *tem* 'have.PRS.3SG' *tinha* 'have.PST.3SG'). Paradigms given in Berrenger (1811: 20) and Fox (1819: xiv-xv) indicate that this was also the case in Callaway's time. In particular, Berrenger's paradigm explicitly equates Creole *tem/tinhe/tinhé* with both *ser* and *estar*.²⁴ Although Callaway (1820b) lists *ser* as 'be', Callaway (1818) does not, nor does Fox (1819). Nevertheless, in (38) Callaway uses *ser* as a copula.²⁵

- (38) **Confia par mi, ser confidento e papia sem**
believe ACC 1SG.ACC **be** (confident) and speak without
importa que vosse te papia bom ou mal.
be.important COMP 2 PRS speak well or badly
'Believe me, **be** confident and speak without minding whether you speak well or ill.' [C 1818: 146]

²⁴Berrenger's examples also occasionally use the zero copula found in modern Creole; see 4 below.

²⁵This example has the additional problem that *confidento* is pure invention; cf. standard Portuguese *confidente* 'confidant', *confiante* 'confident'. The phrase *ser confidento* is omitted from the corresponding example in the 1820 Vocabulary.

3.5.2 Passive auxiliary

Callaway forms the passive with either *tem* or *ser* followed by the past participle (*V-do*) as seen in (39-41). Standard Portuguese uses only *ser* + past participle, but this construction is unlikely to have survived in Sri Lanka Portuguese: Holm et al refer to “a universal tendency for [passive] to be lost during restructuring.” (1997: 97). Modern Creole uses *fikaa* ‘become’ as the passive auxiliary, a formation that appears to have developed partially under Dutch influence (Smith 2010). Berrenger most commonly uses *tem/tinhe* (‘be.PRS/PST’) as the passive auxiliary (42, 43), but *fica* is also occasionally seen (44); no instances of *ser* are found. Fox (1819) gives no passive forms. Berrenger’s data indicate that two passive structures (*tem/tinhe* + *V-do* and *fikaa* + *V-do*) were developed post-creolization, only the second of which survives in modern Creole. Callaway’s use of *ser* is standard Portuguese, not Creole.

- (39) **Vos lo ser soita-dõ.**
 2 FUT *be* whip-PPL.PST
 ‘You will be whipped.’ [C 1818: 127]
- (40) **Eu tem perto per ser foga-do de segura.**
 1SG be near INF *be* stifle-PPL.PST of dryness
 ‘I am almost choked with thirst.’ [C 1820b: 35]
- (41) **Tem falla-do, comtuto, que vosse te papia bemfeito.**
be say-PPL.PST however COMP 2 PRS speak well
 ‘It is said, however, that you speak very well.’ [C 1818: 144]
- (42) **Tem feito.**
be do.PPL.PST
 ‘It is done.’ [B 1811: 106]
- (43) **Furo non tinhe cozi-do.**
 lining NEG *be.PST* sew-PPL.PST
 ‘The lining *was* not sewed.’ [B 1811: 137]
- (44) **Eu te lembra qui vosse lo fica content-ado.**
 1SG PRS think COMP 2 FUT *become* please-PPL.PST
 ‘I believe you will *be* pleased.’ [B 1811: 137, author’s translation]

3.5.3 Pronouns

Callaway (1818: 60) presents a table of pronominal forms that distinguishes between familiar T-forms and polite V-forms and furthermore, makes a distinction (as in English) between possessive forms followed by nouns and independent possessive forms; e.g. *meu* ‘my’, *minha* ‘mine’, *teu* ‘thy’, *tua* ‘thine’, *vosotros-su* ‘your’, *vosse* ‘yours’. This table does not appear in Callaway (1820b).

Reflexes of the familiar T-forms are not found in Indo-Portuguese; Berrenger’s pronominal paradigms show none (1811: 9-12), nor do Fox’s (1819: x). Thus Callaway’s T-forms are an importation from standard Portuguese; they appear only in his paradigms and not in any example in either *Vocabulary*.

Callaway (1818) does generally use *meu* adnominally for the first person possessive pronoun (45a), but occasionally *minha* is also used (46a). Fox lists both *meu* and *minha* as ‘my’. In Callaway (1820b), however, only the form *minha/minhe* appears (45b, 46b). Second person examples use *vosse su* in both *Vocabularies* (47, 48). In standard Portuguese the difference between *meu* and *minha* reflects the gender of the noun modified in both adnominal and independent usages (similarly for *teu/tua*). In Indo-Portuguese creoles only reflexes of *minha* are found: Diu *mĩ* (Cardoso 2009: 127ff.), Korlai *mi* (Clements 2007: 168) and Sri Lanka *mij̃a*. Berrenger’s pronoun paradigms similarly list *minha* as the only 1SG form. *Vosoutros* is a now disused 2nd plural pronoun which survives in modern Creole as *botus*, genitive *botus-su*. standard Portuguese *vossa* is the genitive of the 2nd person pronoun *vós* and can be used with or without a following noun. They survive in the Creole as *vosa/bosa* and *voos/boos*. Berrenger and Callaway also use *vosse* as a nominative form, which must be from standard *você* ‘2SG’; it does not survive in modern Creole. We must conclude that Callaway created the supposed distinction between prenominal and independent forms. Although it was dropped in the 1820 *Vocabulary*, along with the T-pronouns, the inclusion of these features in the 1818 *Vocabulary* indicates that Callaway considered Creole grammar, like its orthography, unfixed and malleable and demonstrates the extent to which he was prepared to impose his own predilections upon it.

- (45) (a.) **Meu** **vide** [C 1818: 82]
 (b.) **Minha** vide [C 1820b: 32]
 1SG.GEN life
 ‘My life’

- (46) (a.) **Elle** **ja** **panha** **ja** **toma** **minha** **livro.** [C 1818: 128]
 (b.) Elle ja panha toma **minhe** livro. [C 1820b: 43]
 3SG.M **PST** pick **PST** take **1SG.GEN** book
 ‘He snatched away **my** book.’

- (47) **Eu tem interamente vosse su.**
 1SG be entirely 2 GEN
 ‘I am entirely *yours*.’ [C 1818: 83, omitted from 1820b]
- (48) (a.) **Eu tem vosse su Servidor.** [C 1818 : 83]
 (b.) **Eu tem vosse-su servidor.** [C 1820b: 32]
 1SG be 2-GEN servant
 ‘I am *your* Servant.’

3.5.4 Definite article *o*

Callaway (1818) frequently uses *o* as a definite article, but this usage is eliminated in the later Vocabulary (31, repeated here as 49, and 50). Modern Creole does not have articles per se, but the numeral *uj* ‘one’ can be used as a singular indefinite marker and the demonstratives *isti* ‘this’ and *aka* ‘that’ are used as definite markers, as in (51, 52) (Smith 2013: 113). Berrenger uses *um* variably as an indefinite marker (53–54), but it appears much more frequently than in modern Creole. She has no definite article (43, repeated here as 55, and 56), but *o* is reflected in frozen collocation with *senhor*, seen in (50). In modern Creole, this combination becomes the honorific 3rd person pronoun *osiir*. Fox also affirms, “There is only one article in the Ceylon Portuguese, and that article is indefinite.” Callaway’s (1818) use of *o* is thus another of his importations from standard Portuguese

- (49) (a.) **O mais levi modo per prende Ignres [sic] tem**
 (b.) Mais leve modo per prende Ingres, tem
DEF most easy way INF learn English be
pera papia-ndo tanto ves-es. [C 1818: 145]
 per papia tanto vez. [C 1820b: 44]
 to/INF speak-NDO many time-PL
 ‘*The* easiest way to learn English is to speak it often.’
- (50) (a.) **Eu lo falla com o mestri.** [C 1818: 124]
 (b.) **Eu lo falla com mestri.** [C 1820b: 43]
 1SG FUT tell with DEF master
 ‘I shall tell *the* master.’
- (51) **Uj buku jaa-oyaa sara leṭar ta-parsa ronal.**
 one book PST-see COND letter PRS-be.visible Ronald
 ‘If I look at a book, *the* letters are visible, Ronald.’ [but my vision for faces is bad]. [Modern SLP; author’s 1974-5 field notes, item 5077]

- (52) **Akandiiya aka sistar-s santaa ta-kuza** ɔɔra.s namaas mee
that.day that nun-PL sit PRS-sew TMPL only FOC
respectu.
respectability.
'Only in those days, when *the* nuns sat and sewed [with the students] was there respectability.' [Nowadays, the nuns give them work and leave them alone, and the girls sit and gossip about their boyfriends etc.] [Modern SLP; author's 1974-5 field notes, item 5278]
- (53) **Da um cadeira por ó.senhor.**
give one chair to **3SG.HON**
'Give the gentleman a chair.' [B 1811: 138, cf. *Da um cadeira por senhor* (idem), 1811: 132]
- (54) **Tem caminho grandé.**
be.PRS road big
'It is *a* highway.' [B 1811: 152]
- (55) **Furo non tinhe cozido.**
lining NEG be.PST sew-PPL.PST
'*The* lining was not sewed.' [B 1811: 137]
- (56) **Ja leva por Rey suva Sentencia...**
PST take to king 3SG.GEN sentence
'[They] took his sentence to *the* king...' [B 1811: 165, author's translation]

3.5.5 Miscellaneous examples

Additional instances are found of Callaway's scant knowledge of Creole grammar. In (57), for example, the suspension points obviously indicate a following complement clause. Callaway ought to have known that *aquele* (modern Creole *aka*) is a deictic determiner/pronoun and not a complementizer.²⁶ This example suggests that Callaway was using a bilingual collaborator to help provide translations of his list of words and phrases. Callaway has failed to notice that his assistant has translated the uniclausal sentence 'Would it not be better, that?'

²⁶The same is true of standard Portuguese *aquele/aquela*. The modern Creole equivalent would involve a conditional clause rather than a complement clause.

- (57) (a.) **Nanda tem mais bom aquel** — [C 1818: 90]
 (b.) **Nada tem mais bom aquel** — [C 1820b: 34]
 FUT.NEG be more good that[DET/PRO]
 ‘Would it not be better that —’

In summary, both of Callaway’s *Vocabularies* are (un)conscious acts of corpus planning that went beyond the selection of conservative features found in the Creole and introduced new characteristics: calques from English, features of standard Portuguese, invented words and grammatical apparatus, and Anglicized syntax. His inconsistent spelling also exhibited standard features that did not correspond to Creole phonology. Nevertheless, Callaway’s examples, like Berrenger’s also reveal South Asian features that characterize modern Creole, demonstrating that they were already present in his time.

4 South Asian features in early 19th Creole

The most obvious examples of typologically South Asian features are occasional examples of OV word order in both Berrenger and Callaway (58-61 and the embedded clause of 62), and in Berrenger alone, postpositions (63, 64) and zero copula (65). Less obvious are the covert expressions of South Asian features in the formal garb of standard Portuguese morphemes. A number of examples of such features are discussed in this section.

- (58) **Eu nade noque faze.**
 1SG *nothing* NEG *do*
 ‘I have *done nothing*.’ [B 1811: 98]
- (59) **Eu nada noco falla.**
 1SG *nothing* NEG *say*
 ‘I say nothing.’ [C 1820b: 36]
- (60) **Ella par.mi nada noco falla.**
 3SG.F 1SG.ACC/DAT *nothing* NEG *say*
 ‘She *said nothing* to me.’ [C 1820b: 37]
- (61) **Eu nada noco fai.**
 1SG *nothing* NEG *do*
 ‘I have *done nothing*.’ [C 1820b: 37]

- (62) **Eu nade tem tempo po eli por olhar hoje.**
1SG FUT.NEG have time ACC3SG INF see today
'I shall have no time to *see him* today.' [B 1811: 132]
- (63) **Qui te lembra vossé coreçam dentro?**
what PRS think 2 heart inside
'What do you think *within* your *heart*?' [B 1811: 95]
- (64) **Non miste papia minhe junto**
NEG OBL speak 1SG.GEN with
'Do not speak to me.' [B 1811: 94]
- (65) **Isti qui minhe Deus?**
this what 1SG.GEN god
'What *is* that, my God?' [B 1811: 95]

4.1 *Tense, Mood, Aspect*

Modern Sri Lanka Portuguese marks TMA categories found in the local languages rather than those of standard Portuguese (Smith 2013: 114ff.). Some of these categories are seen covertly in Berrenger's and Callaway's examples.

4.1.1 Perfective

The modern Creole perfective marker of main verbs is *kaa-* (<*acabar* 'finish'), as in (66). *Cava/caba*, a less reduced form appears in the work of all three early authors. Examples from Callaway and Berrenger are seen in (67-69). One might try to argue that what *caba* (etc.) encodes is not perfectivity, but simply its original lexical meaning 'finish'. It is true that 'finish V-ing' works as a translation for some of these examples: e.g. (68) could be rendered as 'While I finish writing this letter', but for others, it does not: e.g. 'finished dying' is not a possible translation in (69). Thus *caba* is indicating completion of an action/event, rather than encoding the lexical meaning 'finish'. The grammaticalization of *caba* is also consistent with the fact that B inserts it in parts of some verbal paradigms, such as that of *vende* 'sell' (70) where, again, the translation 'finish selling' is inappropriate. Fox similarly inserts *caba* to in his verbal paradigms to indicate perfectivity (71).

- (66) **Numis-kaa-largaa.**
NEG.IMP-PVF-leave
'Don't leave [it].:/ 'Don't give it up.' (Reference is to the house the addressee was renting). [Modern SLP; author's 1974-5 field notes, item 1437]

- (67) **Caba janta qui miste faze?**
PFV dine what OBL do
 ‘What shall we do after dinner? [lit. having dined]’ [B 1811: 144]
- (68) **Ne tempo que eu te caba iscruvé isti carté,**
 in time REL 1SG PRS **PFV** write this letter
 ‘While I make an end of this letter,’ [B 1811: 147]
- (69) **Minhe pai cava morre ja tem dos anno-s.**
 1SG.GEN father **PFV** die PST be two year-PL
 ‘My father has been dead these two years.’ [C 1820b: 40]
- (70) Excerpts from Berrenger’s paradigm of *vende* ‘sell’ [1811: 29-32]
Eu te vende ‘I sell or am selling’
Eu ja vende ‘I sold or did sell’ / ‘I have sold’
Se eu adie caba vende ‘If I had sold’
Quando eu lo vende ‘When I shall sell’
Quando eu ja caba vende / Quando eu lo caba vende ‘When I shall have sold’
- (71) Excerpts from Fox’s paradigm of *prende* ‘learn’ [1819: xi-xii]
Eu ja prende ‘I have learned’ [“preterperfect” indicative]
Que Eu ja prende ‘that I have learned’ [“preterperfect” subjunctive]
Se Eu adie caba prende ‘If I had learned’ [“preterpluperfect” subjunctive]
Quando Eu lo caba prende ‘When I shall have learned’ [“second future” subjunctive]
Ja caba prende ‘Having learned’ [“gerund”]

4.1.2 Future – ancillary functions

One of the non-temporal functions of the FUTURE category of modern Creole is to indicate present likelihood/probability in affirmatives or uncertainty in interrogatives, as seen in (72a), to which the Tamil equivalent is given in (72b). A parallel is also found in Sinhala, but the situation is more complicated because the language marks future time modally through volitive or involitive optatives (Gair 1976). Another function of the future in modern Creole is to indicate a habitual or general (i.e. not time-specific) statement (73). Interrogatives, such as (74), may often be subject to either interpretation. Berrenger also occasionally uses the future marker *lo* non-temporally (13, repeated here as 75) and (76), though this example is from a passage purporting to illustrate Malabar creole.

- (72) a. **Parmi avara mm e[ubattanji lo-tem.**
1SG.DAT now [hesitation] 70 **FUT**-be
'Now I'm **probably** 70.' [Modern SLP; author's 1974-5 field notes, item 5059]
- b. **En-akku oru e[ubattanji irukk-um.**
1SG-DAT around 70 be-**FUT**.3SG
'I'm **probably** around 70.' [Tamil; Author's 1974-5 field notes, item 5059]
- (73) **Aka-ley kriyansa-s mee lo-prenda.**
That-like child-PL EMPH **FUT**-learn
'Only that kind of children learn. [Modern SLP; author's 1974-5 field notes, item 5195]
- (74) **akii lo-tisa?**
Here **FUT**-weave
'Do [the rattan weavers] weave [the chairs] here [i.e. in this workshop]?
[Modern SLP; author's 1974-5 field notes, item 4908]
- (75) **Lo tem aqui disti?**
FUT be here of.this
'Is there of it?' [B 1811: 67. Vieyra's original: *ha lá disso?* (1777:110)]
- (76) **Bos tambem lo bebe?**
2SG also **FUT** drink?
'Do you [also] drink?' [B 1811: 155]

4.1.3 Optative/Permissive

Modern Creole has a optative/permissive marker *jesa-* (< Ptg. *deixa* 'allow, let'), used with 3rd person subjects in affirmative sentences (77), where it is equivalent to Tamil *a[288?][288?]um*, Sinhala *-aave*. Berrenger's *dess*, which he inserts into "imperative" verb paradigms (78) is an earlier form of *jesa-*. Although the semantics of this formation are transparently derived from its constituent parts, *dess* appears to have already been grammaticalized, since it is positioned, like a TMA marker, following the subject and immediately before the verb. Note that this position is only available to third person subjects. Berrenger places *dess* **before** non-third-person subjects, as *dess nosse fazé* 'let us do' (1811: 35). Similarly, Fox's "imperative mood" paradigm of *tem* 'be; have' (79) places *dess* between third person subjects and the

verb. We cannot tell whether this order is permitted for first person subjects, as his sole first person example places the pronoun after the verb. *Deixa(r)* does not survive as an independent verb in modern Creole. Nor does Berrenger list *dess* as an independent verb in his “collection of verbs” (1811: 76-83); it appears in only one of his examples (80), with a hortative meaning and is absent from those examples in which Vieyra uses *deixar*.

- (77) a. [Spkr A] **Inda un doos voo trees pesaam nuku-vii.**
 still one two INDEF three person NEG-come
 ‘Still about two or perhaps three people haven’t come’.
- b. [Spkr B] **Jesa-vii.**
 OPT-come
 ‘Let them come.’ (I.e. the onus is on them to come.) [Modern SLP;
 author’s 19745 field notes, items 5421-5422]

- (78) Optative/permissive *dess* + V in Berrenger (1811)

eli dess tem ‘let him have’ [18]

eli dess da ‘let him give’ [33]

eli dess fazé ‘let him do’ [35]

elotros dess fazé ‘let them do’ [35]

- (79) Fox’s “imperative mood” paradigm for *tem* (1819: xiii)

Tem vos ‘Have thou’

Elli dess tem ‘let him have’

Dess tem nosse ‘let us have’

Tem vosses or *vossotros* ‘have ye’

Ellotros dess tem ‘let them have’

- (80) **Dess olha se tem bem feito**

let see if be.PRS well make.PST.PPL

‘Let us see whether it is well made.’ [B 1811: 137. Vieyra’s original.]

Vejamos se está bem feita (1777: 323)]

4.1.4 Negative system

In the modern Creole of Batticaloa, as in Tamil, the negative system marks aspect and modality but not tense (81, 82; Smith 2013: 115). This system seems already to be at least partially in place in Berrenger's time. For example, modern *nuku-* indicates present, past or near future negation. Likewise, Berrenger's *noque* and Callaway's *noco* make no distinction between PRESENT and PAST. Compare (58, repeated here as 83) with (84) and (85) with (86).

- (81) **Taantu jeentis-pa nuku-falaa.**
many people-DAT NEG-tell
'He *didn't* invite many people.' [Modern SLP; author's 1974-5 field notes, item 1496]
- (82) **Sirviis juustu nun-teem see, nuku-vala, naa?**
work correct NEG-be COND NEG-be.worth no
'If the work is not right, it's *no* good, eh?' [Modern SLP; author's 1974-5 field notes, item 1481b]
- (83) **Eu nade noque faze.**
1SG nothing NEG do
'I *have done* nothing.' [B 1811: 98]
- (84) **Eu noque faze nade.**
1SG NEG do nothing
'I *do* nothing.' [B 1811: 98]
- (85) **Eu noco falla nada.**
1SG NEG say nothing
'I *said* nothing.' [C 1820b: 36]
- (86) **Eu noco fai nada.**
1SG NEG do nothing
'I *do* nothing.' [C 1820b: 37]

4.2 *Nominalization*

In both Sinhala and Tamil nominalized verbs perform a number of syntactic functions, including a common type of clause-embedding. In modern Creole one of the functions of the verbal prefix *ki-* is to nominalize either the entire clause (the translational equivalent of an English infinitive or gerund), as seen in (87), or the unexpressed direct complement of the verb (the translational equivalent of a headless relative), as in (88). Some of Berrenger's examples, such as (29), repeated here as (89), in which *que* is positioned immediately before the verb (or before a tense marker) are strongly suggestive of a verbal noun, since *que* as a relative pronoun is normally positioned at the beginning of the embedded clause. Examples from Callaway are seen in (90-94). The change from (90a) in Callaway (1818) to (90b) in Callaway (1820b) makes the syntax conform to a more European norm, but the meaning has unwittingly been changed to 'I know very well that I have a debt to you.' Examples (92-94) are particularly interesting because they exhibit nominalization of the entire embedded clause, not of just its object, as in the other examples. A further indication that *que* has taken on functions beyond that of complementizer is the fact that Berrenger inserts it into verbal paradigms to translate an English infinitive (95).

- (87) **Tyuvishan ki-ta-daa graandi viraadu.**
 tuition **NMLZ-PRS-give** great error
 'To give tuition [to a child] is a great error.' / 'Giving tuition is a great error.'
 [Modern SLP; author's 1974-5 field notes, item 5394]

- (88) **Tonna, isti biiva-s-pa ki-daa jaa-kaa-daa?**
 next this widow-PL-DAT **NMLZ-give** PST-PFV-give
 'Next, have you given *what [we] give* to the widows?' (I.e. 'Have you distributed the widows' relief funds?') [Modern SLP; author's 1974-5 field notes, item 5420]

- (89) **Non podi intende eli que te falla**
 NEG HBL understand 3SG **NMZR PRS say**
 'One cannot understand *what he says*.' [Berrenger 1811: 98]

- (90) a. **Eu sabe muito bem eu que te deve per vosse.**
 1SG know very well 1SG **NMLZ PRS owe** DAT 2
 'I know very well *what I owe* you.' [C 1818: 86]
- b. **Eu sabe muito bemfeito que eu tem diuda per vosse.**
 1SG know very well COMP 1SG have debt DAT
 2
 'I know very well *what I owe* you.' [C 1820b: 33]

- (91) (a.) **Vosse te intende elle que te falla?** [C 1818: 102]
(b.) **Vosse te intinde elle que te falla?** [C 1820b: 38]
2 PRS understand 3SG.M **NMLZ PRS say**

‘Do you understand *what he says*?’

- (92) (a.) **Huma non podi ouvi otra huma que te**
(b.) **Huma non pode ouvi otro huma que te**
One NEG HBL hear other one **NMLZ PRS**

papia. [C 1818: 101]

papia. [C 1820b: 37]

speak

‘One cannot hear another speak.’

- (93) (a.) **Vos noco faze nada senaõ que te**
(b.) **Vos noco fai nada senaõ que**
2SG NEG do nothing but **NMLZ PRS**

brinca. [C 1818: 124]

brinca. [C 1820b: 41]

play

‘You do nothing but *play*.’

- (94) **Ella ninquere fai nada senaõ que te papia.**
3SG F NEG.HAB do nothing but **NMLZ PRS talk**

‘She does nothing but *prattle*, or *tattle*.’ [C 1820b: 36]

- (95) *que* inserted into verbal paradigms to translate an English infinitive:

qui te vende (Ptg. *vender*) ‘**to sell**’ [B 1811: 31]

qui ja vende (Ptg. *ter vendido*) ‘**to have sold**’ [1811: 31]

qui ja caba anda/ que ja fuy (Ptg. *ter-se ido*) ‘**to have gone away**’ [B 1811: 64]

4.3 Conjunctive participle

A South Asian areal feature is the use of a “conjunctive participle,” a type of serial verb construction, for clausal conjunction (Masica 1976: 108ff.). All but the final verb in a series appear as conjunctive participles, and only the final verb is a main verb carrying the full range of tense, mood and aspect markers. Usually the verbs have a common subject but may each take their own complements. In modern Sri Lanka Portuguese there is no specific marker associated with the conjunctive participle, but it may carry the past prefix *jaa-* or, as in (96), the perfective enclitic =*tu*. This construction appears occasionally in Berrenger (67, repeated here as 97) and Callaway (46, repeated here as 98).

- (96) **Aka noos aka uusha kampani-pa daa=tu, aka**
 that 1pl that Usha company-DAT *give=PFV.PTCP* that
jaa-faya dreetu.
 PST-make right.
 ‘We *gave* that to the Usha company *and* repaired it.’ [Modern SLP; author’s 1974-5 field notes, item 5325]

- (97) **Caba janta qui miste faze?**
 PFV dine what OBL do
 ‘What shall we do *after dinner*? [lit. *having dined*]²⁷ [B 1811: 144]

- (98) (a.) **Elle ja panha ja toma minha livro.** [C 1818: 128]
 (b.) **Elle ja panha toma minhe livro.** [C 1820b: 43]
 3SG.M PST pick PST take 1SG.GEN book
 ‘He *snatched away* [lit. *picked up and* took] my book.’

A negative participle is formed in modern Creole with the preverbal particle *sem* (< Ptg. *sem* ‘without’, a form that survives in modern Creole only as a preverbal marker). An example suggesting this use existed in Berrenger’s time is (99). The expression would be similar in standard Portuguese: *sem ninguem saber*, but the fact that *sem* is positioned directly before the verb and following the subject argues for grammaticalization.

- (99) **Suva Majestado tinhe um dia (incognito) ningum**
 3SG.GEN majesty be.PST one day incognito no.one
sem sabe ne Amsterdam.
NEG.PTCP know in Amsterdam
 ‘One day, his Majesty was incognito (i.e. *without* anyone *knowing*) in Amsterdam.’ [B 1811: 166, author’s translation]

²⁷The interpretation of *janta* as the verb ‘dine’ seems justified, since B lists the words for the noun ‘dinner’ as *jantar* or *cume medié* (1811: 113). But even if one takes *janta* as the noun ‘dinner’, this is still a conjunctive participial construction, with *caba* as the verb ‘finish’ rather than as a PFV marker.

4.4 Reportative

Modern Creole has clause-final REPORTATIVE enclitic =*ski* (<Std. Ptg. *diz que* ‘say.PRS.3SG COMP’ or *disse que* ‘say.PST.1/3SG COMP’), used to mark information the speaker has not directly experienced. The standard Portuguese verb *dizer* ‘say’ survives only in this grammaticalized form. Seen in (100), this common marker is a functional transfer from Sinhala *-lu* / Tamil *-aam*. It is absent from the 19th century texts of which I am aware, nor is it mentioned by Dalgado (1900). However, among the three pages of forms of *fala* ‘say’ that Berrenger lists in his paradigm of the Creole equivalents of standard Portuguese *dizer* (*idem*), the form *disque* appears a single time, in the section titled “Infinitive”, with the gloss ‘he says, or she says’ (1811: 49). It appears again with the same gloss in a section of phrases entitled “to ask” (1811: 96). The only other form of Ptg. *dizer* found in Berrenger is the phrase *que querre dizer?* ‘what means?’ (1811: 96). Indeed, the semantics of *dizer* ‘say; tell’ have been taken over by *falar*, originally ‘speak; talk; tell’, while in turn *papiar*, originally ‘chat’, has encroached on *falar*. Thus *diz que* had likely already fused and become grammaticalized. Explicit, though much later, evidence for such grammaticalization is found in Goonetilleke (1892)²⁸.

- (100) **Aka piskəl-s, etus kii ta-faya=ski, andaa-tu aka pesaam**
 that clerk-PL 3PL what PRS-do=**REP** go-PFC.PPL that person
tɪnə see taam rɛmɛɛdi daa=lav osiɲoor rɛmɛɛdi
 be.PST COND even money give=as.soon.as 3SG.HON money
tomaa-tu te-kaa-levaa=ski, pesaam nun-tem falaa.
 take-PFC.PPL PRS-PFV-take.away=**REP** person NEG-be QUOT
 ‘Those clerks [who serve summonses], what they do **apparently** [is], they go and even if the person is there, as soon as [that person] gives them money [i.e. a bribe] they he [i.e. the clerk], taking the money, takes away [the summons], **apparently**, saying the person isn’t there.’ [Modern SLP; author’s 1974-5 field notes, item 4968]

²⁸The Korlai quotative particle *dəsiki, dəsiki, dəsi* (Clements 2013: 109) has the same source as the SLP reportative, but is likely an independent development. The similarity in form may indicate, however, that *diz/disse que* was a common collocation in Malabar pidgin Portuguese available to be grammaticalized in different ways as subsequent creoles developed.

4.5 *Dative Subject*

One South Asian structure avoided by Berrenger but displayed in one example in Callaway is the use of the DATIVE case to express a non-agentive subject (Masica 1976: 159ff.). Compare (101a) with (102). In Callaway's 1820 edition this example exhibits more standard syntax (101b). A modern example is seen in (72), repeated here as (103).

(101) a. ***Parmi tem quatro.*** [C 1818: 109]

1SG.DAT have four

'I have four [children].'

b. ***Eu tem quatro.*** [C 1820b: 40]

1SG have four

'I have four [children].'

(102) ***Eu tem quatro.***

1SG have four

'I have four [children].' [B 1811: 100]

(103) ***Parmi avara mm e[ubattanji lo-tem.***

1SG.DAT now [hesitation] 70 FUT-be

'Now I'm probably 70.' [Modern SLP; author's 1974-5 field notes, item 5059]

5 Discussion

What do these early grammars reveal about the nature of early 19th C Sri Lanka Portuguese, and what can we conclude about the processes whereby the Creole developed South Asian grammatical characteristics?

Both Callaway and Berrenger present a language that retains many of the typological characteristics associated with other Portuguese-based creoles, but in both authors' works South-Asian characteristics are also variably present. Berrenger is the more reliable witness, given Callaway's apparent unawareness of Creole grammar and his penchant to calque from English and to introduce (mostly lexical) features of standard Portuguese. Berrenger does not appear to be influenced by the standard, except on a few occasions, nor does she often calque from English. Her work is also problematical, however: the form of language she presents is clearly conservative, and she disfavours South Asian features. Some of these characteristics likely escaped her awareness (such as the extended uses of the FUTURE tense). Others, however, such as the ubiquitous postnominal genitive *su*, and head-final

word-order features, must have been actively suppressed. Why would Berrenger favour typologically European features over South Asian features? As noted in section 2, the Burgher community was socially stratified into an educated elite, who identified themselves as “Dutch” and a socio-economically lower group identified as “Portuguese”. While these differences did not align perfectly with ancestry they constituted a significant social divide (cf. Smith 1977: 17-32, McGilvray 1982). Speakers in more isolated communities and those of lower socio-economic levels can be surmised to have had greater contact with Sinhala and/or Tamil, and features of these languages may have been more frequent in their speech. Berrenger may thus have downplayed such features because of their social associations. Given that Berrenger does not fear to differ from standard Portuguese, its influence can be discounted, but she may have favoured typologically European variants because they were judged more appropriate for the intended audience of English-speakers. It is important to note that while Berrenger disfavours South Asian features, she does not eschew them entirely. Consequently, 19th C Sri Lanka Portuguese appears to have been a single variety with a variable, socially correlated mix of South Asian and European features, rather than two distinct varieties. This picture is consistent with Cardoso’s (2014) investigation of the evidence for sociolinguistic variation in Indian Portuguese-based creoles, from the earliest (18th C) records to the present, which reveals varying degrees of differential usage correlating with ethnicity, class, gender and style. As in Sri Lanka, different groups controlled a range of variants, though not everyone likely had access to all variants. Strikingly, Cardoso also finds direct evidence of the type of curation we have seen on the part of both Berrenger and Callaway. Original questionnaires returned from Mahé, found in the Schuchardt archives at the University of Graz, exhibit some quite dissimilar translations by two respondents, Mr. d’Cruz and Mr. Rozario, some of which are shown in Table 3. As Cardoso points out, d’Cruz’s responses are more basilectal than those of Rozario. For example, d’Cruz has OV word order in the third sentence and optionally in the second sentence, while Rozario gives only VO order; d’Cruz uses the postnominal genitive in the fourth example, while Rozario uses the preposition *de*. D’Cruz’s forms are also more basilectal: *quilai* in the first example, instead of standard *como*, *cume* instead of *come* and *fruitos* instead of *frutos* in example three. Cardoso discovered that d’Cruz was the first to fill out the questionnaire and that Rozario had access to d’Cruz’s responses when filling out his version. Cardoso remarks, “Rozario’s version was, therefore, in effect a correction of d’Cruz’s, one that eliminated forms and constructions we now find in Modern creole in favour of Portuguese-inspired (and French-inspired) ones.” (2014: 100).

Because both Berrenger and Callaway disfavour typologically South Asian features, we can be sure that such features were more prevalent in early 19th C Sri Lanka Portuguese than appears, at first glance, from their works. Indeed, the Creole may have possessed some South Asian features not attested in Berrenger

Tab. 3: Differing translations from two Mahé respondents to Schuchardt's questionnaire (Cardoso 2014: 98).

English	Mr. d'Cruz	Mr. Rozario
'How are you?'	Quilai tem vos?	Como tem vos?
The inkpot is on the table.	Tintera tem riva de meza. / Mezasse riva tintera tem.	Tinteira tem riba de meza.
We are eating fruits	Os fruitos te cume.	Nos te come frutos.
Roof of the house.	Cazás cumé.	Cume de caza.

and Callaway. One likely such feature is the use of *oras(untu)* 'hour-PL(-LOC)' as a clause-final element marking temporal clauses, as seen in (104) and (52, repeated here as 105). Since Malabar Indo-Portuguese has a very similar element (106) it likely developed during Portuguese rule, when the two regions were in contact.²⁹ At the same time, in the early 19th C, South Asian features had not supplanted the typologically European features to the extent that they have today, though some registers would likely have exhibited fewer European features than others. Thus early 19th C Creole was a way-station on the path to South Asianization: a point at which both European and South Asian features were variably present and in competition.

(104) **Ta andaa oras isti onda vii kadii.**

PRS go *TMPL* this way come IMP

'**When** you go, come by here.' [Modern SLP; author's 1974-5 field notes, item 1473]

²⁹Hugo Cardoso (p.c., July 2016) notes that *com* (Ptg. 'with') as a coordination marker is another likely early feature, as it appears in some other Luso-Asian creoles. Clements (2009: 57ff.) surveys diverse nominal marking functions marked by reflexes of *com* in both Luso-African and Luso-Asian creoles.

- (105) **Akandiya aka sistar-s santaa ta-kuza** ɔɔra.s namaas mee
that.day that nun-PL sit PRS-sew **TMPL** only FOC
respectu.

respectability.

‘Only in those days, when the nuns sat and sewed [with the students] was there respectability.’ [Nowadays, the nuns give them work and leave them alone, and the girls sit and gossip about their boyfriends etc.] [Modern SLP; author’s 1974-5 field notes, item 5278]

- (106) **Prēdisə -pə ja- foy** ɔrzə, **purtəgez ja- iskusew**
education -DAT PST- go.PST **when** Portuguese PST- forget
foy

go.PST

‘**When** [we] went for education, [we] forgot Portuguese.’ Malabar Indo-Portuguese [Cannanore; free-flowing speech, field data] (Cardoso 2013: 7)

A few South Asian characteristics may have been present very early in the Creole, particularly features found in other Portuguese-based Asian creoles, such as the postnominal genitive marker *-su*, and the above-mentioned temporal marker. Comparative work will doubtless lead to the identification of others. Such work must be sensitive to the possibility of parallel development, particularly since Dravidian and Dravidian-like languages are the adstrates in both Sri Lanka and Malabar. For example, both Sri Lanka Portuguese and Malabar Portuguese have a clause-final element marking conditional clauses, seen in (51, repeated here as 107, and 108). Despite the similarity of these structures, the conditional element is not identical (*see/sara* in Sri Lanka; *sana* in Malabar),³⁰ and there is a subtle difference in detail: the Sri Lanka construction requires that the verb be in the past tense, while this restriction does not apply in Malabar. Moreover, Sri Lanka retains a preverbal conditional marker *kam/kanda* < *quando* ‘when’ (109). Since convergence with South Asian typology has produced left-branching structures (hence no prefixes) in Sri Lanka Portuguese, this preverbal marker is likely older than the typologically South Asian structure with clause-final *see/sara*.

³⁰An anonymous reviewer suggests that both forms may derive from Portuguese *senão* (‘if not; or else’). Phonologically, the derivation of Sri Lanka Portuguese requires the denasalization of *n* to *r*, which is not found elsewhere in the language. Moreover, *senão* already has the reflex *sena* in SLP, which can occur as a sentence-final discourse particle with the meaning ‘so, then, in that case’; it is unlikely that *senão* would have developed two quite different discourse functions in similar syntactic positions.

- (107) **Um buku jaa- oyaa sara lɛ̃tar ta- parsá rɔnal.**
 one book PST- see COND letter PRS- be.visible Ronald
 ‘If I look at a book, I can see the letters, Ronald.’ [Modern SLP; author’s
 1974-5 field notes, item 5077]
- (108) **Ola -kādə, tə- gosta sana, da kaza.**
 look -PTCP PRS- like if give marry
 ‘After seeing [her], if [they] like [her], [we] give [her] away in marriage.’
 [Malabar Indo-Portuguese: Cannanore; free-flowing speech, field data,
 Cardoso 2013: 6]
- (109) **Avara aka -pa riiva vɔnda kam- andaa, noos naada**
 now that -DAT above side COND- go 1PL nothing
naa- poy faya.
 NEG.POT- HBL do
 ‘Now if it goes above that, we can’t do anything.’ [Modern SLP; author’s
 1974-5 field notes, item 5562]

Abbreviations

ACC accusative, ASSOC associative, B Berrenger, C Callaway, COMP complementizer, COND conditional, DAT dative, DEF definite, Du. Dutch, F feminine, FOC focus, FUT future, GEN genitive, HAB habitual, HBL habilitative (‘can’), IMPR impersonal, INDEF indefinite, INF infinitive, INS instrumental, LOC locative, M masculine, MOD. modern, N noun, NEG negative, NMLZ nominalizer, OBLG obligative (‘must’), OPT optative, OV object verb (word order), PFV perfective, PL plural, POT potential, PP prepositional/postpositional phrase, PPL participle, PRF perfect, PRO pronoun, PRS present, PST past, PTCP participle, Ptg. (standard) Portuguese, QUOT quotative, RED reduplication, REL relative, SG singular, STD standard, SLP Sri Lanka Portuguese, SVO subject verb object (word order), TMA tense/mood/aspect, TMPL temporal (‘when’), V verb, vbl. adj. verbal adjective, VO verb object (word order).

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